

Little Minds Big Hearts: Teachers' Views on Socio-Emotional Development of Learners

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Abstract. Socio-emotional development is a foundational aspect of a child's holistic growth, particularly in elementary school when emotional habits and interpersonal skills begin to take shape. This study explored the lived experiences of elementary teachers in fostering socio-emotional development among students, recognizing their pivotal role in shaping young learners' emotional well-being. In-depth interviews were conducted with selected elementary teachers using a qualitative phenomenological approach. Thematic analysis revealed two emerging themes highlighting teachers' views on socio-emotional development: learner-centred relationships and diverse learner backgrounds. Furthermore, teachers reported that they rely on coping mechanisms such as peer collaboration, mindfulness and empathy, and emotional resilience to navigate their roles' emotional and relational challenges. As for educational insights, collaborative school culture and policy and training support emerged as key enablers of socio-emotional initiatives. These findings emphasize the importance of emotionally responsive teaching grounded in meaningful relationships and institutional backing. The study recommends that educational leaders and institutions enhance training, support systems, and policies that promote emotionally supportive environments, allowing teachers and students to thrive.

KEY WORDS

1. Socio-emotional development 2. elementary teachers 3. elementary teachers' views

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1. Introduction

The foundation years of a child's life are the most critical in shaping who they will become. During these formative years, children gradually collect blocks of knowledge, experiences, and emotional understanding that will help them construct their sense of identity and navigate the world around them. Being surrounded by individuals, teachers, family, and caregivers—who nurture their growth in a holistic manner is essential to this process. In the early stages of education, teachers held a particularly important role, as they not only impart academic knowledge but also significantly contribute to the development of children's socio-emotional skills. Through fostering empathy, communication, and emotional resilience, teachers help lay the groundwork for children to thrive both socially and emotionally throughout their lives. On a global scale, studies have emphasized the significance of socio-emotional development (SED) in children, with increasing recognition of its long-term impact on academic

and social success. Socio-emotional development plays a crucial role in fostering resilience, collaboration, and effective communication, all of which are essential in today's world (Greenberg, 2023). A study by UNESCO (2019) found that students with strong socio-emotional skills tend to perform better in school, build stronger relationships, and handle stress more effectively. These skills are not only important in childhood but also in adulthood, where they help individuals navigate professional and personal challenges. Another systematic review in Asia further stated that socio-emotional development is closely linked to school readiness and success, as well as long-term well-being. The development of emotional regulation, empathy, and positive social interactions during elementary years is a predictor of better outcomes in both school and life. This review emphasizes the cultural differences in how these skills are developed and expressed, but the importance of these competencies remains universal (Yong, et al., 2023). Children who are well-supported in their socio-emotional growth tend to exhibit better mental and physical health, making the investment in these skills vital for educators and policymakers worldwide. It coincides with the study conducted in Ghana by Moreno-Gomez and Cejudo (2019). It explored how social-emotional development is influenced by factors such as social skills, empathy, and relationships in elementary education. The paper examined how assessments of these skills impacted children's ability to regulate emotions and behavior in kindergarten settings. The findings highlighted the importance of regularly assessing social-emotional skills to foster mental, behavioral, and self-control abilities, which are crucial for healthy interpersonal interactions. This leads to the conclusion that teachers play a key role in guiding this development by modeling positive behaviors and consistently supporting students' socio-emotional growth. In the same vein, studies in the Philippines have also empha-

sized the significance of socio-emotional development in children, particularly in the context of education with the primary movers which are the teachers. UNICEF (2023) highlighted the development of socio-emotional skills assessments aimed at helping educators and policymakers understand the role these skills play in children's academic achievement and psychological well-being. The study outlines various frameworks for socio-emotional learning (SEL) and discusses initiatives by the Philippine Department of Education to integrate SEL into the curriculum. The paper underscores the necessity for comprehensive assessments to gauge socio-emotional skills, which are critical for successful learning environments. However, fostering socio-emotional development among young children is easier said than done. A study focused on the socio-emotional perspectives of Filipino learners from kindergarten to Grade 10, revealing how cultural contexts shape their emotional and social development. The research explored the challenges faced by educators in fostering these competencies among students, advocating for the integration of socio-emotional learning into teacher training programs. This approach is essential for promoting a holistic educational experience that aligns with the unique socio-cultural landscape of the Philippines. (Reyes and Rungduin, 2019). Another study by Rana (2022) explored the socio-emotional development of students, emphasizing the need for tools that assess and enhance these crucial skills. The research, supported by UNICEF, aims to help educators and policymakers understand the importance of socio-emotional learning (SEL) in fostering student success in academics, psychological well-being, and future employment. This study highlights the gap between international and local initiatives and provides recommendations to address these challenges within the Philippine educational system. Meanwhile, in the local scene, Cardenas (2018) emphasizes the critical role

of teachers in fostering socio-emotional development among students. One significant study conducted by the World Bank assessed teaching practices across various public primary schools in Mindanao. It identified socio-emotional skills as a key component of effective teaching, highlighting that teachers who integrate these skills into their lessons help create a supportive classroom environment. This approach is essential for promoting student well-being and enhancing academic performance, as it encourages positive relationships and emotional regulation among young learners. In terms of the status of learner's socio-emotional development in the local setting, Gumban (2024) conducted a study about the socio-emotional development of students in Marilog District B. She opined that the elementary years are a critical period for children's socio-emotional development. In rural areas, however, children may face additional challenges that could negatively impact their development, such as limited access to resources and fewer opportunities for socialization. The study unfolded the importance of teacher interaction in students' socio-emotional development. In summation, several systematic reviews focusing on social-emotional development across Asia, including the Philippines, indicated that socio-emotional skills are vital for academic success and long-term well-being. However, these studies have identified gaps in existing studies and called for more focused research on the contexts that influence socio-emotional learning as well as how teachers foster the socio-emotional development of their students (Reyes, 2019). This underscores the necessity of equipping teachers with the knowledge and strategies to effectively support children's socio-emotional growth, par-

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This phenomenological study explores and analyzes the experiences and strategies employed by elementary school teachers from schools within the district of Montevista, Davao de Oro in develop-

particularly in diverse educational settings. Taking into consideration the cited problem situation, I found it timely to conduct this study. This brought the necessity to conduct an inquiry about the experiences and strategies of teachers in fostering the socio-emotional development of students as well as values that are deemed necessary and useful. I hope that this study enlightens the identified sectors of the academe. This includes the educational leaders, school heads, teachers, other stakeholders, and future researchers. Educational leaders can benefit from the findings of this study because it can provide them with insights and valuable lessons regarding the state of the socio-emotional development of students and how teachers are helping them in that aspect. Also, they can utilize the results and find ways to better enhance and improve the ways and strategies necessary for the socio-emotional development of students. The findings of this study might help the school heads or principals to be aware and informed about the socio-emotional development strategies by the teachers and find ways to offer some help, guidance, tools, and assistance to them. The teachers can benefit from this study by looking into the findings and learnings from the experiences of teachers in helping in developing the socio-emotional skills of the students. The stakeholders may provide better support to better enhance the strategies for the socio-emotional development of the students. Finally, this would be helpful to future researchers as an additional contribution to their references for future research in the field of socio-emotional development among students and how it is reshaping the way teachers can help students in that particular aspect.

ing their students' socio-emotional skills. I hope that the study will provide useful insights into the strategies used by teachers for the students' socio-emotional development. Ultimately, I will strive so that the study will help increase my un-

derstanding of how to effectively utilize teaching strategies as an elementary educator in order to help my students grow and flourish as individuals, and to cater to their needs. The central objective of this data collection revolved around capturing the real-life experiences of elementary school teachers as they utilize strategies for the socio-emotional development of their students. The outcomes of this phenomenological study provided me with a deeper understanding of how teaching is a transformative profession and how teachers can help in

honing important facets and skills necessary for growth. Furthermore, I will assess the efficacy of these strategies in elevating the socio-emotional development of the students. The valuable insights obtained from this study possess the potential to exert a positive influence on various aspects of inclusive education and teaching, professional development initiatives, and educational policies aimed at cultivating empowering and supportive learning environments within classrooms.

1.2. Research Questions—This study explores the experiences and strategies of elementary school teachers in fostering their students’ socio-emotional development. The research is carried out with the purpose of addressing the following inquiries:

- (1) What are the views of elementary school teachers in student’s socio-emotional development?
- (2) What are the coping mechanisms of elementary school teachers in socio-emotional development?
- (3) What educational management insights can be formulated from the findings of the study?

1.3. Definition of Terms—For a more comprehensive understanding, the following terms were described operationally. Socio-emotional development This refers to the broad term used to describe a child’s social and emotional competence, temperament, and behavioral regulation (Hally and Darling-Churchill, 2019). Emo-

tional regulation This refers to the ability to exert control over one’s own emotional state. It may involve behaviors such as rethinking a challenging situation to reduce anger or anxiety, hiding visible signs of sadness or fear, or focusing on reasons to feel happy or calm (Psychology Today, 2020).

1.4. Theoretical Lens—The theoretical underpinning of the study was anchored on the Social Emotional Learning (SEL) Theory coined by Shriver and Weissberg (1987, as cited from Routledge, 2023). The theory describes the process through which children learn and develop their emotional intelligence and social skills. It is a theory of learning that focuses on helping children develop the capacity to recognize and manage their own emotions, set and achieve goals, understand and empathize with the emotions and experiences of others, build positive relationships, and make responsible and healthy

decisions. Social Emotional Learning emphasizes the importance of developing a range of social and emotional skills that are essential for success in both personal and professional settings. By teaching children these skills, we can help them become more well-rounded, empathetic, and resilient individuals. As applied in the context of the study, the Social Emotional Learning Theory fully encapsulates the importance of socio-emotional development among students. It captures the great essence of helping and guiding children in determining, recognizing, and managing their emotions. Ele-

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

mentary education is a child’s first structured social environment outside the family. Developing socio-emotional skills helps children learn how to form healthy relationships, cooperate, and resolve conflicts, which are essential skills they will use throughout life. The study was further reinforced by the Sociocultural Theory by Lev Vygotsky (1962, as cited in Nurfaidah, 2018). This theory emphasizes that children learn and develop through social interactions, particularly with more knowledgeable others, such as teachers, parents, and peers. Vygotsky believed that teachers play a critical role in guiding children through their learning process by providing scaffolding—support, and guidance that help children achieve a higher level of understanding than they would on their own. In the context of the present study, elementary school teachers provide support in learning ac-

tivities, gradually reducing that help as the students become more competent, allowing them to internalize the knowledge. It highlights the importance of the teacher’s role in elementary education by focusing on their ability to shape children’s development, meaningful social interactions, and guidance. The theories mentioned is useful in allowing the researcher to fully comprehend and understand the phenomenon being studied. The Socio-Emotional Learning Theory enables the researcher to grasp how the learners develop socio-emotional learning. The theory illuminates how learners develop the capacity necessary for socio-emotional development. Meanwhile, the Sociocultural Theory accentuates the role of knowledgeable others, in this case, the elementary school teachers. Thus, the theories guide the researcher in building an understanding of the study conducted.

2. Methodology

This chapter effectively addresses the specific objectives of the study by outlining the systematic procedures and methodologies used in phenomenological research. It also explains the selected research design and the roles I played as the researcher throughout the study’s implementation. Moreover, it offers thorough insights into the research subjects, clarifying their procedures and selection standards. The chapter concludes by exploring the techniques used for data collection,

analysis, and strategies used to uphold ethical standards during the research.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—A study’s philosophical and qualitative presumptions are vital in steering the investigation. Four fundamental assumptions form the bedrock for comprehending qualitative research: ontological, epistemological, axiological, and methodological. These assumptions establish the groundwork for the research design and inform the researcher’s approach to the study. A paradigm is a broad framework or perspective that guides and shapes how researchers approach their studies, formulate research questions, gather data, analyze findings, and interpret results. It encompasses a set of beliefs, assumptions, methodologies, and theoretical foundations that influence how researchers conceptualize and conduct their research (Zukauskas et al., 2018). In this research, the paradigm guided the choice of methodology, methods, and techniques, shaping the overall research process and ensuring coherence in the study.

Ontology This section of the study focuses on the relationship between the problem and reality. According to Creswell and Poth (2018), ontology can be defined as the study of the nature of reality. The authors also assert that the research participants’ perceptions of reality are varied and subjective. This study recognizes the complexity and diversity of the realities faced by elementary school teachers in fostering the socio-emotional development of their students. Every teacher’s story adds to a diverse yet collective understanding of their experiences. It is my sole responsibility to use theme analysis to capture these various realities and provide a thorough picture of the experiences, strategies, and values that teachers have in their strategies for fostering socio-emotional development.

Epistemology Epistemology deals with the nature of knowledge and the relationship between the knower and the known. According to Creswell and Poth (2018), the researcher made an effort to reduce the gap between them and the participants based on the epistemological premise. By engaging directly with the participants, I became an “insider,” facilitating a more authentic and nuanced collection of data. This approach supports the gathering of firsthand experiences and coping mechanisms, which are critical in exploring the subjective realities of the participants.

Axiology It concerns the influence and importance of my values as a researcher in this study. According to Creswell and Poth (2018), acknowledging and openly discussing the researcher’s values that shape the study is crucial. The values which influence how data are interpreted and presented are explicitly acknowledged in the research process. As a researcher, I will handle each participant’s narrative with care and integrity, and I have the utmost respect for the information they provide. This commitment guarantees that the experiences of the teachers are communicated truthfully, mirroring both their individual and research values.

Methodology According to Crotty (2020), this is “the strategy, plan of action, process, or design lying behind the choice and use of particular methods and linking the choice and use of the methods to the desired outcomes.” Its objectives are to explain, assess, and defend procedures. This study explores the experiences and coping mechanisms of elementary school teachers in fostering the socio-emotional development of their students. In order to support the ontological and epistemological tenets, certain techniques like focus groups and interviews are employed, enabling a thorough and sympathetic examination of participants’ stories. These techniques were chosen because they can successfully convey the complexity and depth of the participants’ experiences.

Rhetoric In research, rhetoric is the skillful and convincing use of language, communication strategies, and presentation tactics to effectively communicate

concepts, claims, and conclusions in order to sway the audience's opinion and comprehension of the study (Beqiri, 2018). I will utilize an engaging and respectful narrative style that honors the voices of the participants while ef-

fectively communicating the significance of the findings. This method not only makes the research easier to read but also guarantees that the interpretations are strong and based on the experiences of the participants.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Using a phenomenological research methodology, my goal is to explore the experiences and coping mechanisms of elementary school teachers in fostering the socio-emotional development of their students from the schools within the district of Montevista, Davao de Oro. My objective is to gather information about their experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights in relation to the phenomenon I am studying. Utilizing phenomenology as my guiding qualitative framework, I seek to uncover the essence and significance of the roles played by these individuals, emphasizing their unique viewpoints and the intricate details of their experiences. As the study's qualitative researcher, I will support a level of investigation that goes beyond

cursory observations. My research aims to investigate the experiences and coping mechanisms of participants in relation to the phenomenon. I emphasize the significance of understanding the complexities of the human experience in light of the various perspectives that are shaped by unique contexts, backgrounds, and personal histories (Neubauer et al., 2019). To capture the profound and complex nature of socio-emotional development, my study places a strong emphasis on in-depth interviews, reflective dialogues, and the analysis of participants' narratives. I hope to contribute a thorough and contextually rich understanding of the experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights related to socio-emotional development all while upholding phenomenological principles.

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—Determining the precise approach used in a study is crucial in order to customize the best research design, data collection strategy, and data analysis approach to the study's objectives. I used a qualitative research design in this investigation. Hammerley (2013, cited in Aspers and Corte, 2019) states that studies characterized by verbal rather than statistical analysis are appropriate for qualitative research. Since I am studying the lived experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights of elementary school teachers in fostering the socio-emotional development of their students, the qualitative design is the most appropriate. This means that rather than establishing or refuting theories, I described and elaborated this phenomenon. There are, however, specialized methods used in qualitative research, including

grounded theory, narrative, case studies, phenomenology, and ethnography. Using a qualitative phenomenological research design, I explored the lived experiences of the participants in this particular setting. I selected this approach because, according to Asper's (2009, cited in Aspers and Corte, 2019) work, the scientific side of phenomenological research focuses on communicating the viewpoints of the subjects and the importance of their experiences, then applying scientific concepts to analyze these perspectives. Furthermore, according to Creswell (2018), a phenomenological study is a method of inquiry that describes the complex and collective experiences of the participants with respect to a particular phenomenon. A key idea in phenomenology is to reduce one's interpretations of a particular phenomenon to a description that

can be applied to all situations. Therefore, my goal is to identify a phenomenon that revolves around the participants' experience of socio-emotional development. I collected information

2.4. Research Participants—Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most or all perceptions. Obtaining most or all the perceptions leads to the attainment of saturation. Saturation occurs when adding more participants to the study does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (2017) as cited in Hennink and Kaiser (2022) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (2018) recommends 5 to twenty-five 25. According to Subedi (2021), larger samples in qualitative studies hinder an in-depth exploration of the study phenomenon. There are no specific rules when determining the appropriate sample size in qualitative research. Qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 2002 as cited in Mullet, 2018). With this, the participants of this study were ten (10) elementary school teachers from three (3) different schools within the

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Ethical considerations are crucial because they relate to the moral principles and guidelines that govern my conduct as a researcher. These principles ensure that I carry out my investigations responsibly, treating participants with respect and striving to generate reliable and precise information. To protect participants, maintain scientific integrity, and foster trust within the research community, I adhere to established ethical standards in my

from people who have direct experience with this phenomenon in order to create detailed and accurate descriptions.

district of Montevista, Davao de Oro. These schools are the following: Banglasan Elementary School, Sambayon Elementary School, and Camansi Elementary School. To gather a more diverse and in-depth understanding of the experiences and coping mechanisms of elementary school educators regarding socio-emotional development, participants were selected from each school. This selection process ensures that the study captures a broad range of perspectives allowing for a more comprehensive examination of developing students' socio-emotional development. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: they must be teaching in one of the three schools within Montevista District, they must be teachers for more than 3 years, they must be elementary school teachers, and willing to participate in the study. I will utilize the universal sampling design so that the participants are chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2018). It is also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996 as cited in Vasileiou et al., 2018).

research practices (Resnik, 2020). Social Value This concerns the potential benefits and favorable outcomes that research can bring to society, like addressing problems or improving people's quality of life. I evaluate the societal value of my study by acknowledging its potential impact and importance for the larger community. This ensures that resources are directed toward research that has the potential to create significant advantages for society.

Informed Consent

This involves obtaining a participant's voluntary agreement to participate in a research study after they have been provided with sufficient information about the study's purpose, methods, potential drawbacks, and benefits. In this research involving teachers, it is my responsibility to ensure that both the participants fully understand the study and their rights. This explanation allowed them to make an informed decision about participation, thereby preserving the teachers' autonomy and dignity.

Vulnerability

The vulnerability of research participants pertains to their increased risk of experiencing harm, exploitation, or coercion due to factors such as age, cognitive ability, or socioeconomic status. As a researcher, it is crucial for me to acknowledge and consider the potential vulnerability of these participants and take appropriate measures to protect them. This involves providing additional safeguards and support, such as obtaining informed consent from the teachers, ensuring confidentiality, and carefully explaining their rights and the study's procedures in a way they can understand. Additionally, I modified research methods to minimize potential adverse effects, ensuring that the well-being of these participants is prioritized throughout the study.

Risks, Benefits, and Safety

In research, it is essential to carefully evaluate the potential risks and benefits associated with participation in a study, as well as to implement measures that safeguard the well-being of participants. These elements involve assessing the potential disadvantages and advantages of participating in a study, along with establishing strategies to ensure the welfare of participants. In this investigation, as the researcher, I meticulously assessed and balanced these factors, ensuring that the potential benefits outweigh the risks. I put adequate precautions in place to minimize harm while optimizing the safety of

participants, particularly considering the vulnerabilities of participants. This comprehensive approach is crucial to maintaining ethical standards and protecting the participants throughout the research process. Privacy and Confidentiality Privacy and confidentiality in research are about safeguarding participants' personal information and ensuring their identity remains confidential unless they explicitly consent to disclosure. In the context of this study, I am responsible for implementing appropriate protocols to secure participants' data and maintain confidentiality. This includes anonymizing data, securely storing information, and limiting access to authorized personnel only. These measures are crucial to protect the privacy of participants and uphold the integrity of the research process.

Justice

This concept relates to the equitable allocation of both the advantages and disadvantages resulting from research across various segments of society. In this study, I ensured that my research is inclusive, avoiding the exploitation or exclusion of vulnerable groups. Additionally, I strived to make the benefits of the research accessible to all who could benefit from it. This approach promotes fairness and equity throughout the research process, ensuring that no group bears an undue burden or is left out of the potential gains from the findings.

Transparency

Transparency in research encompasses maintaining integrity at every phase of the study, from its conception and execution to the reporting of results. In this study, I offered clear and truthful information regarding my research methodologies and outcomes. Furthermore, I am receptive to examination and feedback. Transparency acts as a catalyst for trust, credibility, and accountability, not only within the research community but also among the general public. This commitment to openness ensures that the process and results of my research are

accessible and understandable to all stakeholders involved.

The Qualification of a Researcher

The qualification of a researcher relates to one's academic background, professional experience, and proficiency in a particular area of study, ensuring that one possesses the requisite abilities and knowledge to conduct the research competently. In this investigation, I held suitable qualifications that showcase my capability to conduct research, analyze data, and interpret the results. My expertise and training provide the foundation necessary to approach this study with a rigorous scientific method and critical analytical skills, ensuring the integrity and validity of the findings.

The Adequacy of Facilities

This addresses the presence and suitability of the essential resources, tools, and infrastructure required to execute a study efficiently and securely. In this research, I guaranteed access to appropriate facilities for conducting the investigation. This access facilitates the creation of credible and consistent findings and mitigates potential risks to study participants. Having the right facilities ensures that the data collection and analysis processes are conducted under conditions that uphold the highest standards of

research integrity and safety.

Community Involvement

This encompasses the dynamic involvement and active engagement of community members, stakeholders, or the intended study population throughout the research journey, from initial planning to sharing research outcomes. In this study, I engage the community to guarantee the study's relevance, acceptability, and potential impact. Additionally, this involvement fosters trust and cooperation between me and the community. Engaging with the community not only helps to tailor the research to be more effective and meaningful but also enhances the overall quality and applicability of the results.

Plagiarism and Fabrication

Researchers should strictly follow principles of academic honesty and integrity. This entails giving proper credit to the work of others, presenting original contributions, and verifying the accuracy and authenticity of data. In this study, I employed tools like plagiarism detectors and maintain thorough documentation of my research procedures to ensure that my work is devoid of plagiarism and that all data and discoveries are authentic and reliable. By upholding these principles, I enhanced the credibility and trustworthiness of the research community.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—As an unbiased research facilitator and promoter, I am responsible for ensuring that the research process is conducted fairly, objectively, and without personal bias, prejudice, or influence from outside sources. I create an environment that encourages the open and honest exploration of ideas and promotes fairness in data collection and analysis. This commitment to impartiality helps to uphold the integrity of the research process and ensures that the findings are reliable, and representative of the true phenomena being studied. As an expert in qualitative methods, I am familiar with various qualitative research

techniques, such as interviews, focus groups, and participant observation. I possess the skills and knowledge necessary to design, conduct, and analyze qualitative studies, ensuring that the research question is satisfactorily addressed and that the results are legitimate and dependable. My expertise in these methods allows me to deeply explore complex social phenomena and capture the nuanced experiences of participants, contributing to the validity and reliability of the research findings. As a data collector and keeper, I gathered information from various sources such as interviews or observations, and I ensure accurate and secure storage of this

information. I followed ethical guidelines, safeguard participants' privacy, and ensure that data is structured and available for later examination and understanding. This careful management of data helps maintain the integrity of the research process and supports the production of credible, reliable findings that can be reviewed and utilized by others in the academic community. As a data analyst, I analyzed the gathered data to discover trends, patterns, and valuable perspectives in accordance with the research query. I utilized meticulous qualitative data analysis methods like coding and thematic analysis to extract significant findings and enrich the knowledge base within my discipline. This approach allows me to deeply understand the data, providing insights that are not only relevant but also

contribute significantly to the field, enhancing scholarly discussions and practical applications related to the study topic. Finally, as an organizer and presenter of data, I am tasked with synthesizing and communicating the research findings concisely and coherently. This entails skillfully conveying the study's objectives, approaches, outcomes, and ramifications through written documents, presentations, or alternative means of transmitting information. I ensured that the research results are easily accessible and comprehensible to the designated audience. This approach helps to maximize the impact of the findings, ensuring they are not only shared but also understood and utilized by others in ways that can further knowledge and influence practice in the field.

2.7. Data Collection—In the gathering of data, this study employed a systematic procedure. Several steps were taken in adherence to the proper data collection procedure. This was done in order to ensure the accuracy and objectivity of the data collection. The following is the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed.

Securing endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School, the Schools Division Superintendent, and the School Principal

To initiate the data collection process, I secured endorsements from key stakeholders including the Dean of the Graduate School at Rizal Memorial Colleges, the Schools Division Superintendent, and the School Principal. This process involves submitting formal letters outlining the research objectives and methodology, accompanied by any supporting documents. This crucial step took place within the last two weeks of October 2024 ensuring that all necessary permissions are in place before proceeding with the collection of data. This proactive approach not only facilitates compliance with ethical standards but also fosters a cooperative

environment among all parties involved.

Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent Upon receiving the endorsement, I requested permission from the school's division superintendent. This requires submitting a formal letter detailing the research proposal and its significance to the educational community. Along with the letter, I attached Chapters 1 and 2 of my dissertation and the research instrument, clearly explaining the study's objectives and the process of participant identification. Moreover, I waited for the response from the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) before proceeding with the data collection. This step was done during the first two weeks of November 2024, ensuring that all necessary approvals are in place to conduct the research ethically and effectively.

Asking for permission from the school heads Once permission is granted, I sought approval from the school heads of the selected institutions. This step involves submitting formal request letters to each school head, outlining the research's purpose and the expected data collection timeframe. I asked for permission to con-

duct the study from the third week of November 2024 to the last week of the same month. Obtaining consent from the participants With school heads' approval, I asked consent from the research participants, through informed consent forms. These forms clearly explain the research purpose, participant rights, and confidentiality measures. This consent process ensures that participants are fully informed and agree to participate. Asking for consent from participants were done in the last week of November 2024. Conducting the interview Upon securing consent from all participants, I scheduled and conducted the interviews using a structured or

2.8. *Data Analysis*—After collecting the data, I embarked on data coding and thematic content analysis. This involves methodically structuring the transcribed data into categories, subcategories, and themes from the interview dialogues. By discerning patterns and connections within the data, I formulated conclusions and glean insights directly related to the research objectives. This process allows me to interpret the data effectively, ensuring that the findings accurately reflect the experiences and perspectives of the participants. In this study, I employed Creswell's Thematic Analysis approach, which is particularly suited for encompassing a range of perspectives and portrayals in participants' feedback. Adopting thematic analysis authenticates the portrayal of individual components and facilitates the categorization of identified patterns within the provided responses. Thematic analysis is a qualitative research technique used to recognize, scrutinize, and interpret patterns or themes present within qualitative data in textual, visual, or other formats. As a qualitative research approach, thematic analysis allows researchers to systematically arrange and dissect complex data sets. It involves searching for overarching themes that encapsulate the narratives embedded within the

semi-structured interview guide to ensure consistency and reliability in data collection. The interviews took place in the first two weeks of December 2024.

Transcribing the responses of the interviewees Following the interview sessions, I meticulously transcribed the interviewees' remarks, taking diligent account of non-verbal cues and contextually relevant details. This procedure utilized audio recordings and field notes to comprehensively capture the breadth of participants' reactions. The transcription of interviewee responses was done for the third week of December 2024.

data. This process necessitates the identification of themes through meticulous examination and repeated review of transcribed data (Dawadi, 2020). This methodical approach helps ensure that the analysis is both comprehensive and reflective of the data collected, providing deep insights into the study's objectives. Therefore, I used Creswell's Thematic Analysis in my research, which necessitated extensive theming and transcript interpretation. According to Caulfield (2020), there are multiple essential phases in Creswell's Thematic Analysis, including familiarization, coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, defining and labeling themes, and writing up. I became fully immersed in the intricacies and subtleties of the content as I become acquainted with the data to begin this process. After that, I started categorizing the data using semantic richness to group different informational components. I created themes that encapsulate the main ideas of the data using these codes. After that, these themes are examined and improved upon to make sure they appropriately depict the dataset. Every theme has a definition and name that elucidates the fundamental ideas. The last step entails combining the themes and insights into a cohesive article that clearly conveys the study's conclu-

sions. This methodical approach guarantees a comprehensive examination and enhances the comprehension of the information.

2.9. Framework of Analysis—The analytical framework in phenomenological research is a methodical and structured approach to data analysis, interpretation, and presentation. In this research study, I made use of Colaizzi’s method to analyze data from the interviews and discussions with the participants regarding their lived experiences in fostering the socio-emotional development of their students. According to Morrow et al. (2021), Colaizzi’s (1978) method features a distinctive seven-step process that offers a rigorous analysis, closely adhering to the data at each stage. This method culminates in a concise yet comprehensive description of the phenomenon under study, which is validated by the participants who experienced it. The effectiveness of this approach relies on rich first-person accounts of experiences, which can be collected through various means. Although face-to-face interviews are common, data can also be gathered from written narratives, blogs, research diaries, online interviews, and other forms. This method enables researchers to uncover emergent themes and explore the intricate relationships between them (Wirihana et al., 2018).

Data Familiarization By reading and rereading the transcripts several times, I aim to fully understand the meanings conveyed by the participants and gain a global sense of their experiences and coping mechanisms for the socio-emotional development of students. This thorough review process is crucial for fully grasping the nuances of participants’ statements, enabling a deeper analysis of their experiences.

Identifying Significant Statements I carefully identified every statement in the narratives that is directly related to the phenomenon I am studying. In order to identify and highlight phrases and descriptions that shed light on the particular experiences under study, a thorough examination of the gathered data—such as written narratives or transcripts of interviews—must be conducted. This step is essential to ensuring that my analysis stays on topic and provides a strong basis for future thematic development.

Formulating Meanings After carefully examining the important statements, I determine meanings that are pertinent to the phenomenon. Although Colaizzi admits that complete bracketing is never truly possible, I have to reflexively “bracket” my own presuppositions to stick closely to the phenomenon as experienced. To guarantee that the analysis stays rooted in the participants’ real experiences, this process entails putting aside my own interpretations as much as is practical.

Clustering Themes I ensured a rigorous analysis that remains true to the participants’ experiences and coping mechanisms for socio-emotional development by grouping the identified meanings into themes that are shared by all accounts. Throughout this process, presuppositions must be bracketed, especially to avoid any possible influence from existing theories. By letting the themes naturally arise from the data rather than being influenced by outside forces, this preserves the integrity of the analysis.

Developing an exhaustive description I incorporated every theme generated in the previous step into a comprehensive and all-encompassing description of the teachers’ experiences and coping mechanisms that I wrote. By identifying common themes from the participant accounts, this thorough description seeks to convey the essence and complexity of the phenomenon. Taking this step, ensured that the final representation presents a comprehensive perspective of the experiences that each participant has had.

Producing the fundamental structure I broke down the lengthy explanation into a succinct, concise statement that highlights the key ele-

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study)

ments that I believe are crucial to understanding the phenomenon’s structure. The essence of the participants’ experiences is effectively and concisely communicated through this succinct synthesis, which concentrates on the essential components that are necessary for comprehending the phenomenon.

Seeking verification of the fundamental structure I asked participants if the fundamental structure statement accurately reflects their experience, either by returning it to all partic-

ipants or, in larger studies, to a subsample. I might go back and change the earlier stages of the analysis in light of their comments. Through this iterative process, the validity and credibility of the findings are increased, and the analysis is kept firmly based on the perspectives of the participants. The following figure illustrates this rigorous process, highlighting each step to comprehensively explain the actions taken to comprehensively analyze the data.

2.10. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—The trustworthiness of a study is about how reliable,

sensible, and authentic the research results are, ensuring that the conclusions are trustworthy

and accurate. In qualitative research, factors like credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability are often used to evaluate how reliable the study is. These considerations are further described below, according to Guba and Lincoln (1981, as cited by Creswell, 2018). Credibility Building credibility entails proving that the results are accurate. Credibility is important for this study because it evaluates if the results accurately represent the realities and experiences of elementary school teachers in fostering socio-emotional development of their students. Capturing the truth and honest answers of the participants and analyzing them truthfully would build my study's credibility. I conversed with the participants for a long time in order to gain a thorough understanding of their experiences and to increase my credibility. I also used triangulation, gathering information from a variety of sources, including observations, interviews, and maybe questionnaires. In order to confirm the interpretations, I gave the participants a preliminary version of the findings as part of member checking.

Transferability The degree to which the results of this study can be used in different situations or with different populations is referred to as transferability. While the particular insights are closely linked to elementary school teachers in fostering the socio-emotional development of their students, the results would contribute to the field of education, specifically in teaching pedagogy since it entails the development of students' socio-emotional skills. I gave thorough explanations of the research context and methodology. The study's transferability increased because this thorough, rich narrative enables others, including educators, school ad-

ministrators, and researchers, to assess how well the results apply to comparable contexts or populations. **Confirmability** Confirmability deals with the study's objectivity by making sure that the respondents, not my personal prejudices or biases, shaped the findings. I implemented a thorough audit trail that details every step of the research process, from data collection to data analysis decisions, in order to ensure confirmability. I documented every step of the process, especially the data collection and the responses of the participants regarding their experiences and coping mechanisms for students' socio-emotional development. This methodological transparency makes it possible for other researchers to evaluate the research's objectivity by following the study's development and going over the choices made. **Dependability** Dependability is proving that the study results are reliable and repeatable in similar situations. Dependability in this study was attained through meticulous documentation of the entire research procedure, including the methods used for data collection and analysis. By ensuring that other researchers can duplicate the study and possibly produce consistent results, such documentation validates the dependability of the research. By following these standards, the research not only offers valid and trustworthy conclusions regarding elementary school teachers in fostering the socio-emotional development of their students, but it also offers a framework that researchers and other educators can use to compare similar learning environments. This methodology enhances the study's standing in the academic community and provides insightful information for upcoming studies and instructional design.

3. Results and Discussion

This section of the study delves into elementary teachers lived experiences of socio-emotional development among students. It centers on the research questions and insights drawn from participants' firsthand narratives, illuminating public elementary school teachers' diverse perspectives

and practices.

3.1. Views of Elementary Teachers in Socio-Emotional Development—Elementary teachers often see their role extending beyond academic instruction to nurturing the whole child, recognizing that socio-emotional development is foundational to students' success inside and outside the classroom. They emphasize the importance of creating a safe and supportive environment where students feel valued and understood. It enables children to express their feelings, develop empathy, and build meaningful relationships. More so, their perspectives reveal a deep commitment to helping students navigate challenges, build resilience, and develop confidence- understanding that these socio-emotional competencies are critical for lifelong learning and personal growth. This leads to the first research question, highlighting elementary teachers' views on fostering their students' socio-emotional development. The responses from the participants collectively delve into two emerging themes: learner-centered relationships and diverse learner backgrounds.

3.1.1. Learner-Centered Relationships—In every classroom lies a dynamic relationship that quietly shapes how children grow, connect, and learn. Teachers speak of the subtle, everyday moments- welcoming smiles at the door, gentle encouragement during moments of frustration, and listening intently when a student needs to be heard- as the foundation of their work. These acts are not just about maintaining order or guiding behavior; they are intentional efforts to build trust, foster emotional security, and create spaces where students feel genuinely seen and supported. Through these nurturing connections, teachers find the opportunity to guide not just minds but hearts. This profoundly human aspect of teaching emerged clearly in participants' voices, who shared stories that reflect how these relationships shape their daily practices and expe-

riences. The participants strongly agreed that promoting socio-emotional development significantly builds stronger teacher-student relationships. Specifically, participants highlighted the value of listening and connecting with learners. These experiences are consistent with Askeland (2019), who emphasized fostering social-emotional skills such as empathy, relationship-building, and decision-making at an early age. Students who feel emotionally supported and connected are more likely to succeed academically and socially. As a result, it becomes clear that teachers prioritizing emotional development create a learning environment conducive to academic and personal growth. However, the varying emotional needs of students make it difficult for teachers to balance academic instruction and emotional support. Emotional needs can range from mental health issues and social anxiety to family-related concerns, all of which can hinder students' educational engagement. This challenge was evident in the responses of participants, which mentioned the need to be more patient and understand students' emotional situations. According to research by Clunies-Ross, Little, and Kienhuis (2019), these emotional challenges often result in behavioral issues that stress teachers and disrupt classroom instruction. Hence, teachers educate and consistently adapt their strategies to meet their learners' emotional and behavioral needs. Teachers are also facing a challenge in balancing academics and the emotional growth of students. Teachers' primary duty is to assist and guide students in learning. However, they are also expected to nurture the students' development, such as their socio-emotional growth. Balancing academic rigor with emotional development presents a significant challenge for educators, participants underscored how teachers assume dual roles- academic facilitators and emotional caregivers. Allbright et al. (2019) highlight

that focusing on academics and SEL is essential for holistic student development, yet balancing the two can be demanding and complex in daily practice. Furthermore, Kariou et al. (2021) point out that teachers face significant challenges due to the emotional labor required in managing both academic expectations and the emotional needs of their students. Emotional labor includes showing empathy and maintaining a positive attitude, even when stressed. This ongoing pressure and the expectation to achieve academic goals can lead to teacher burnout. Participants in related studies, like R5, highlighted the importance of patience and understanding, underscoring the stress teachers feel in emotionally demanding situations. Overall, participants in the study noted a growing awareness of the need for mindful and emotionally aware teaching practices. Educators can create an inclusive and supportive classroom environment that fosters students' overall development by addressing underlying issues rather than just the visible symptoms of student behavior.

3.1.2. Diverse Learner Backgrounds—Students enter the classroom carrying stories shaped by their home life, culture, and personal experiences. Some come from supportive environments, while others face daily struggles that affect their focus and participation. Teachers often adjust their methods to connect with learners who vary in academic ability, emotional readiness, and background. These differences may not be visible initially, yet they significantly impact how students engage with lessons and peers. Over time, teachers realize that a one-size-fits-all approach falls short, pushing them to become more flexible and responsive to each learner's unique needs. Classrooms today reflect a rich mix of learner identities shaped by varying backgrounds and emotional experiences. Teachers have observed that

students differ widely in academic capabilities, emotional readiness, and social maturity. Their upbringing, home environment, and socioeconomic conditions often shape these differences. Collie (2022) emphasized that students' emotional needs are highly individual and influenced by age, background, and personal challenges. The sense of connection to others, often referred to as "relatedness," is crucial for students' emotional and social well-being, which in turn fosters their academic engagement. However, responding to this diversity is no small task. Teachers must constantly adapt their instructional and emotional support strategies to meet the unique needs of each learner. This often involves modifying classroom routines, communication styles, and even disciplinary approaches to suit the varying personalities and emotional profiles present. Research from the American Institutes for Research (2021) highlights the difficulty of individualizing emotional support within a large group, noting that students with anxiety, for instance, may need calm and structure, while others may require more guidance and intervention. Balancing these competing needs while ensuring academic progress significantly demands teachers' time, energy, and emotional capacity. Addressing students' emotional needs with diverse backgrounds is a dynamic and ongoing process. It requires empathy, cultural awareness, and the capacity to respond flexibly to various emotional expressions and behaviors. With the right support systems in place, teachers can foster learning environments where all students- regardless of their emotional or cultural starting points- are allowed to succeed both academically and personally. Figure 3 shows the views of elementary teachers in socio-emotional development and the emergence of the two themes: Learner-centered relationships and diverse learner backgrounds.

Fig. 3. Views of Elementary Teachers in Socio-Emotional Development

3.2. *Coping Mechanisms of Elementary Teachers in Socio-Emotional Development* —

The role of teachers exceeds cognition growth—it crosses over other developmental domains of students. More so, they are entrusted to nurture socio-emotional development, which fosters resilience, empathy, and positive interpersonal relationships. Teachers are prompted to navigate students' emotional needs in the dynamic and often challenging classroom environment while maintaining academic focus. These demands call for adaptive and intentional strategies that support the emotional well-being of young learners. Understanding how teachers respond to and manage these responsibilities provides insight into their professional resilience and highlights the practices that cultivate emotionally supportive learning spaces. In line with this, the second research question centers on the coping mechanisms and strategies applied by elementary teachers in fostering the students' socio-emotional development. Based on the responses, three emerging themes were found: Peer collaboration, mindfulness and empathy, and emotional resilience.

3.2.1. *Peer Collaboration*—In the face of growing emotional and social challenges in the classroom, teachers have increasingly turned to strategies emphasizing connection, cooperation, and mutual support among students. By creating opportunities for learners to work together, share perspectives, and engage in meaningful dialogue, educators aim to nurture essential interpersonal skills and emotional awareness. These approaches enhance classroom harmony and provide students with practical tools to navigate their feelings and relationships more effectively. This emphasis on interaction and shared experience emerges clearly in the reflections of participants, who described various practices that promote student collaboration and contribute to the overall socio-emotional growth of their learners. In addition to this, the study of Woods (2022) emphasized the advantage of collabora-

tive activities in enhancing students' academic engagement while also building persistence and motivation, which are important indicators of long-term educational success. As students engage with their peers, they learn to manage their emotions, support one another, and develop the ability to persevere when facing difficulties. Moreover, the American Psychological Association (2020) stresses that effective teaching practices incorporating peer collaboration, such as group projects, class discussions, and cooperative learning, enhance students' ability to communicate, solve interpersonal conflicts, and express empathy. These social interactions are instrumental in helping students feel connected to their learning environment. When students work collaboratively, they learn academic content and practice vital life skills in communication, conflict resolution, and empathy, which contribute to their socio-emotional well-being. Participants also noted that understanding student behavior through social interaction is critical. The Journal of Positive Behavior Interventions by the Hammill Institute (2024) supports this perspective by explaining that classroom dynamics and peer relationships can significantly influence students' behavior. Disruptive actions often manifest stress or unresolved peer conflicts, highlighting the need for collaborative strategies where students feel heard and supported. Teachers who promote peer-based problem-solving help students manage interpersonal challenges more constructively. Finally, emotional safety, which the participants repeatedly mentioned, was identified as essential for meaningful peer interaction. The National Center on Safe Supportive Learning Environments (2019) states that when students feel emotionally safe, they are more willing to participate, share their thoughts, and form authentic relationships with their peers. This emotional safety, bolstered through structured peer collaboration, helps students build resilience, explore their emotions in a non-threatening environment, and

support one another in overcoming academic and social challenges.

3.2.2. Mindfulness and Empathy—In fostering students' socio-emotional development, teachers often rely on practices that encourage self-awareness, emotional regulation, and sensitivity toward others. These approaches create classroom environments where students are guided to understand their feelings while also learning to recognize and respect the emotions of their peers. Students build a foundation for more compassionate and respectful interactions through these subtle yet intentional strategies. The importance of creating emotionally safe spaces also emerged strongly from participant narratives. The National Center on Safe Supportive Learning Environments (2019) emphasized that students who feel secure expressing their emotions are likelier to participate in learning and social exchanges with openness. This sense of safety makes it easier for students to listen with empathy, engage in respectful dialogue, and show compassion to classmates facing difficulties. Such an environment encourages students to pause, consider their words and actions, and develop a more profound sensitivity to the emotional climate around them. As teachers model emotionally grounded behavior, they also navigate their internal challenges. Kariou et al. (2021) explored the emotional labor of consistently demonstrating care, patience, and attentiveness in classroom interactions. Sustaining this level of emotional presence requires teachers to manage stress and maintain composure, even under challenging situations. Developing internal coping mechanisms rooted in mindfulness helps teachers remain calm and responsive, enabling them to guide students with clarity and empathy. This emotional balance becomes a powerful influence in the social-emotional climate of the classroom. A similar focus on emotional modeling is seen in the work of Aske-land (2019), who emphasized the long-term value of helping children learn how to under-

stand their feelings and those of others. When teachers intentionally guide students through social experiences like sharing, decision-making, and resolving misunderstandings, they reinforce behaviors grounded in empathy. These daily moments become opportunities for students to reflect on how their actions affect others and to choose more thoughtful responses— an essential step in forming strong, respectful relationships. Further reinforcing this, Yong et al. (2023) found that students who develop emotional awareness early in their educational journey are more likely to thrive socially and academically. While shaped by cultural context, the review highlighted how these competencies remain universally essential for building supportive peer connections and positive learning outcomes. When teachers nurture these skills through consistent, reflective interactions, students learn to recognize the emotions of others, respond with kindness, and contribute to a classroom environment where empathy becomes the norm. Overall, Moreno-Gomez and Cejudo (2019) stressed the importance of consistently assessing and supporting students' emotional growth. Their study in early education revealed that children who were guided to identify their feelings and understand the emotional experiences of peers exhibited greater self-regulation and social cooperation. This intentional focus on emotional development, led by teachers who model understanding and patience, plays a critical role in shaping a school culture where students learn to care, listen, and connect meaningfully with one another.

3.2.3. Emotional Resilience—In daily classroom challenges, teachers often draw from an inner strength that allows them to remain steady, supportive, and responsive to their students' needs. This capacity to adapt to emotionally demanding situations, maintain calm, and continue guiding students with patience plays a crucial role in shaping a positive learning environment. As they navigate conflicts,

setbacks, or moments of emotional distress among learners, teachers rely on this strength to model healthy coping strategies and create spaces where students feel encouraged to do the same. Teachers often face emotionally demanding situations that require them to remain composed, supportive, and responsive despite internal or external stressors. Collie (2022) highlighted how students thrive in connected and supported environments. Still, this sense of relatedness cannot be nurtured unless teachers are emotionally equipped to maintain those connections. Teachers can respond constructively to their students varied emotional needs by practicing emotional resilience- staying calm and grounded. This resilience sustains classroom harmony and demonstrates to learners how to cope with their own emotional challenges. In maintaining a safe and supportive learning space, teachers are constantly managing their emotional responses while addressing those of their students. The National Center on Safe Supportive Learning Environments (2019) emphasized that emotional safety is foundational to student development. For teachers, upholding this safety involves a daily commitment to patience and emotional regulation. Teachers must consistently draw upon their emotional strength, whether managing conflict, supporting a distressed student, or guiding group dynamics. Their ability to model calmness and empathy, even under pressure, becomes a powerful tool in teaching students how to handle emotions

3.3. Educational Insights in Socio-Emotional Development—Through their daily classroom experiences, teachers develop meaningful understandings of how to support the whole child. Over time, they see that fostering emotional and social growth is as crucial as academic instruction. As they guide students through learning tasks and personal challenges, educators observe firsthand the power of em-

pathy, consistency, and community in shaping behavior and well-being. These insights often extend beyond individual practice, highlighting the value of shared responsibility and supportive structures within the school system. Two key patterns have emerged from these reflections—emphasizing the importance of a Collaborative School Culture and the need for Policy and Training Support in sustaining socio-emotional

constructively. Emotional resilience also underpins a teacher’s ability to remain committed to student growth, especially when faced with setbacks or persistent behavioral issues. Greenberg (2023) noted that socio-emotional development requires consistent reinforcement, which demands stability and perseverance from educators. Teachers who demonstrate resilience can navigate frustrations, maintain supportive relationships, and adjust their approaches without losing focus on their students’ well-being. This ongoing emotional effort becomes a protective factor for students and educators, allowing them to continue fostering growth even in challenging conditions. Finally, Gaither (2019) pointed out that reinforcing effort rather than outcome helps students develop confidence and persistence. For teachers, promoting this mindset requires emotional resilience- especially when student progress is slow or uneven. It takes strength to encourage, motivate, and celebrate effort amid pressure for results. Teachers who persist in recognizing small gains and supporting students through frustration become anchors of emotional support in the classroom. In modeling these qualities, they guide students toward academic success and long-term emotional competence. Figure 4 shows the coping mechanisms of elementary teachers in socio-emotional development and the emergence of the three themes: Peer collaboration, mindfulness and empathy, and emotional resilience.

Fig. 4. Coping Mechanisms of Elementary Teachers in Socio-Emotional Development

development efforts.

3.3.1. Collaborative School Culture—
 In many classrooms, students’ emotional and social growth is not nurtured by a single effort but by a collective commitment that spans the entire school environment. Teachers often find that their ability to support students’ socio-emotional needs is strengthened when shared values, consistent practices, and open communication are present among colleagues. A sense of unity among educators creates a network of support that extends to students, shaping a culture where everyone feels safe, understood, and valued. Within this environment, socio-emotional learning becomes more than an isolated practice- it becomes a shared mission. The insights shared by the participants affirm the importance of building strong, collaborative relationships within the school community to support students’ socio-emotional development. Allbright et al. (2019) emphasize that students benefit emotionally and academically

when teachers and parents communicate consistently. Teachers who take time to understand their students’ home environment and emotional needs are better equipped to provide appropriate guidance and support. This collaboration improves emotional regulation and strengthens the foundation for student success. In support of this, Chen and Rivera-Vernazza (2023) observed that digital tools have become valuable in enhancing teacher-parent collaboration. With the increasing demands on educators and families, technology offers flexible and accessible ways for communication to thrive. Teachers can maintain close contact with parents through emails, messaging apps, and online meetings, encouraging their involvement in the child’s educational journey. These tools help bridge the gap between home and school, fostering shared responsibility for students’ growth. In addition, the Varkey Foundation (2020) underscores the value of creating opportunities for parents to participate in school events and activities. Teachers

report that hosting exhibitions of student work or school programs brings parents into the learning environment meaningfully. These events serve as celebrations of student achievement and touchpoints for building relationships and cultivating a community that supports learning and emotional development. This intentional effort to include parents strengthens the collaborative culture across the school. Chase (2024) further reinforces that partnering with parents is essential to a teacher's role, particularly in guiding student development. Teachers face a range of experiences when forming these partnerships, but they recognize the significant impact that consistent collaboration has on creating emotionally supportive learning environments. Involving families in the educational process helps extend social-emotional learning beyond the classroom, ensuring that students receive encouragement and reinforcement at home. Ultimately, the National Center on Safe Supportive Learning Environments (2019) notes that family engagement is a cornerstone of a positive school culture. When parents actively participate in their children's education, it fosters a shared sense of belonging and connection. This collaborative dynamic between home and school strengthens students' emotional safety and contributes to an environment where academic and social development can flourish. The following participant responses reflect how this culture of collaboration becomes vital in supporting students' well-being.

3.3.2. Policy and Training Support— Teachers often navigate complex emotional and academic needs in the classroom, requiring personal dedication and a strong system of institutional backing. As teachers strive to foster their students' socio-emotional development, clear structures, supportive frameworks, and access to relevant professional growth become essential. The alignment of school priorities with teacher needs ensures that their efforts are not isolated but reinforced by consistent guid-

ance and capacity-building. These structural supports not only enhance classroom practices but also empower educators to respond effectively to the evolving demands of their profession. Teachers consistently emphasized the importance of institutional support in effectively promoting socio-emotional learning. This view echoes the findings of Reyes and Rungduin (2019), who examined the socio-emotional perspectives of Filipino learners from kindergarten to Grade 10. Their study revealed that cultural context significantly shapes emotional development and pointed to the need for integrating socio-emotional learning into teacher preparation programs. Doing so would ensure that educators are equipped with context-sensitive strategies aligned with the diverse emotional needs of learners. Bishop (2022) added that teachers serve as the primary implementers of SEL programs, and their success heavily depends on proper training. With structured guidance, teachers can address students' emotional and behavioral needs from varied backgrounds. The presence of formal training programs empowers educators to integrate SEL into daily classroom practices, ultimately benefiting the emotional development of all learners. In a broader view, Reyes (2019) pointed out that the notable gaps in the implementation of socio-emotional development stem from the lack of context-specific strategies and insufficient access to sustained professional development for teachers. As a result, there is a pressing need for educational policies that prioritize socio-emotional learning while simultaneously offering continuous training opportunities tailored to local classroom realities. In addition, Kariou et al. (2021) addressed the emotional burden many teachers carry due to the absence of systemic support. Their research revealed that emotional labor—often unacknowledged by institutional policies, significantly contributes to teacher burnout. They argued for establishing policy frameworks that acknowledge the emo-

tional demands of teaching and embed supportive measures that protect educators' well-being and effectiveness in fostering emotionally responsive classrooms.

3.3.3. Emotionally Responsive Practices— In classrooms where young children are nurtured academically and emotionally, teachers often take roles beyond delivering lessons. They become attentive listeners, caring guides, and steady sources of comfort during times of uncertainty. These educators recognize that supporting a child's emotional well-being is essential to creating a safe and encouraging learning environment. Through thoughtful actions such as acknowledging emotions, providing calm spaces, and using a gentle tone, they help children feel respected and understood. Collie (2022) reinforced this perspective by exploring how teachers' sensitivity to student emotions influences classroom climate. The study found that when educators practiced emotional attunement, such as noticing students' moods, acknowledging their feelings, and responding with empathy, students developed stronger emotional regulation skills. These emotionally responsive interactions led to increased student engagement and a greater sense of belonging. In their review of SEL programs, McCabe and Altamura (2019) concluded that the most effective interventions were those that emphasized both skill development and emotional responsiveness. Programs that succeeded in promoting socio-emotional growth included teachers who adapted strategies based on students' emotional cues and needs. This responsiveness ensured that students not

only learned emotional vocabulary and behaviors but also felt emotionally supported during the learning process. Bishop (2022) highlighted the importance of professional development in cultivating emotionally responsive teaching practices. Her findings revealed that educators who were trained in SEL frameworks demonstrated greater confidence in addressing emotional issues in the classroom. These teachers reported stronger connections with students, particularly those from emotionally or socially marginalized backgrounds, supporting the idea that responsiveness fosters inclusion and emotional safety. Additionally, Hassani and Schwab (2021) examined the impact of SEL interventions on students with emotional and behavioral challenges. Their study emphasized emotionally responsive delivery. This includes adjusting strategies to match each child's emotional profile, which was found crucial to the success of these programs. Teachers who were able to modify their approach based on student behavior and emotional signals saw significant improvements in students' emotional regulation and interpersonal skills. Taken together, these insights reveal the vital role that structured policy initiatives, well-supported training opportunities, and emotionally responsive practices play in enabling educators to cultivate socio-emotional growth in students meaningfully. Presented in figure 5 encompasses the educational insights in socio-emotional development and the emergence of the three themes: collaborative school culture, policy and training support, and emotionally responsive practices.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter provides a summary of the study. I have drawn conclusions regarding the implications and future directions based on the findings. The aim of my study is to explore the experiences of elementary teachers, their coping strategies, and their insights into educational management as they promote socio-emotional development in their students.

Fig. 5. Educational Insights in Socio-Emotional Development

4.1. *Findings*—I employed thematic analysis and a qualitative phenomenological approach to accomplish the research goals. To authentically grasp people’s experiences, open-ended interview questions were used following Creswell’s (2018) recommendations. Additionally, by using this interviewing technique, I encouraged my participants to wholly and freely express how they define or interpret the phenomenon under investigation- the role of fostering socio-emotional development in the experiences and narratives of elementary teachers. Based on the study’s results, the thematic analysis revealed the following emerging themes: elementary teachers’ views in fostering socio-emotional development include learner-centered relationships and diverse learner backgrounds. Meanwhile, the coping mechanisms applied by elementary teachers surfaced three themes: peer collaboration, mindfulness and empathy, and emotional resilience. Lastly, the educational management insights of elementary teachers are summarized into three emerging

themes: collaborative school culture, policy and training support, and emotionally responsive practices. The first set of themes emerged from elementary teachers’ views on fostering socio-emotional development. One major theme was learner-centered relationships. Teachers emphasized the importance of building strong, trusting relationships with their students, recognizing that individualized attention and genuine care are fundamental in supporting students’ socio-emotional growth. This approach allows teachers to understand better and respond to students’ unique emotional needs. Another significant theme was diverse learner backgrounds. Teachers acknowledged the variety of cultural, social, and emotional experiences students bring to the classroom, influencing their socio-emotional development. Recognizing and valuing this diversity was essential in creating an inclusive environment that nurtures every student’s emotional well-being. The second thematic area explored the coping mechanisms employed by elementary teachers. The first identified cop-

ing strategy was peer collaboration. Teachers often relied on colleagues for emotional and professional support, sharing strategies and experiences that helped them manage the complexities of fostering socio-emotional development in the classroom. Mindfulness and empathy emerged as a second coping mechanism. Teachers practiced mindfulness to maintain emotional balance and employed empathy to better connect with students and colleagues. These skills helped them navigate stressful situations and create a compassionate classroom atmosphere. Emotional resilience was also a key coping mechanism. Despite the emotional demands of their role, teachers demonstrated the capacity to recover from setbacks and maintain a positive outlook. This resilience enabled them to sustain their commitment to supporting students' socio-emotional growth. Finally, the study revealed insights into educational management from the perspective of elementary teachers. One important theme was the need for a collaborative school culture. Teachers stressed that a supportive, cooperative school environment enhances their ability to foster socio-emotional development effectively. When administrators, staff, and teachers work together, the collective effort benefits students' emotional well-being. The second key insight was the significance of policy and training support. Teachers highlighted the importance of school policies that prioritize socio-emotional learning and the availability of ongoing professional training. These supports equip teachers with the knowledge and skills to address their students' socio-emotional needs effectively. Lastly, the study emphasized the role of emotionally responsive practices. Teachers underscored the importance of being attuned to students' emotional states and responding with empathy and care. Such practices create a safe and nurturing classroom environment where students feel valued, understood, and supported in their emotional development. These themes highlight the challenges and opportunities in

fostering socio-emotional development in elementary education and provide valuable insights into how educational management can better support teachers in this vital process.

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed several significant findings related to elementary teachers' lived experiences, coping mechanisms, and educational management insights in fostering socio-emotional development among students. The first key implication is that learner-centered relationships and recognition of diverse learner backgrounds are fundamental in supporting students' socio-emotional growth. These findings confirm the principles of Social Emotional Learning (SEL) Theory, which emphasizes the development of self-awareness, social awareness, and relationship skills as core components of student well-being and academic success. Teachers' focus on individualized emotional support aligns with SEL's aim to foster positive interactions and emotional regulation, reinforcing the theory's practical relevance in elementary education. Moreover, the emphasis on diverse learner backgrounds underscores the need for culturally responsive teaching, which SEL theory advocates as essential for equitable socio-emotional development. Furthermore, the findings also validate Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory, which highlights the importance of social interaction and cultural context in cognitive and emotional development. Teachers' coping mechanisms, including peer collaboration and creating a collaborative school culture, reflect the sociocultural view that learning and development occur through social engagement and shared experiences. The teachers' use of empathy and mindfulness as coping strategies further exemplifies the internalization of socially mediated emotional regulation, a key process described in sociocultural theory. This insight suggests that socio-emotional development in students is deeply interconnected with the social environment created by educators and peers. The

coping mechanisms identified, such as peer collaboration, mindfulness and empathy, and emotional resilience, imply that teachers need access to supportive professional networks and training that foster emotional self-care and collegial support. Educational leaders and policymakers should prioritize creating opportunities for teacher collaboration and provide resources for mindfulness and socio-emotional skills training, which can enhance teachers' capacity to support their well-being and that of their students. From an educational management perspective, the themes of collaborative school culture, policy and training support, and emotionally responsive practices highlight the necessity of systemic support to sustain socio-emotional development initiatives. Schools must cultivate environments where staff work cooperatively, share best practices, and feel supported by clear policies that value socio-emotional learning. Professional development programs tailored to socio-emotional competence, emotionally responsive teaching, and culturally relevant strategies will better prepare teachers to meet the diverse needs of their learners. Embedding these supports into the fabric of school management assists institutions in creating nurturing spaces where both teachers and students thrive emotionally and academically. In conclusion, this study illustrates that fostering socio-emotional development requires teacher commitment and robust support systems at the institutional level. The findings confirm SEL and Sociocultural theories, reinforcing the theoretical foundation for current educational practices and policies. Addressing these implications reinforce academic institutions to better support elementary teachers in nurturing the holistic development of their students, ultimately contributing to healthier, more inclusive learning environments.

4.3. Future Directions—According to the study's findings, it is essential that the insights obtained be clearly communicated and utilized by the key stakeholders for whom this research

was intended.

Learners

The findings offer meaningful benefits for learners, who are at the heart of socio-emotional development in the classroom. When teachers are emotionally supported and equipped with effective coping strategies, learners experience more compassionate, responsive, and supportive instruction. Future directions for learners involve the implementation of student-centered socio-emotional learning activities that promote self-awareness, empathy, and positive social interactions. Schools can incorporate inclusive and culturally sensitive practices that affirm learners' identities and encourage active engagement in their emotional and social growth. Involving learners in reflective practices and collaborative learning experiences strengthens their emotional intelligence and helps them develop essential life skills. These efforts contribute to a school environment that values emotional well-being and supports the overall development of each learner.

Teachers

The study's focal beneficiaries are the teachers themselves. They can use the findings to reflect on their current practices and better understand their students' socio-emotional needs. The study highlights practical coping mechanisms- peer collaboration, mindfulness and empathy, and emotional resilience- that teachers can adopt to maintain their emotional well-being while enhancing their ability to support students. Furthermore, the findings may encourage teachers to build stronger professional networks, share effective strategies, and advocate for a classroom culture centered on emotional intelligence and mutual respect.

School Heads

The findings are valuable to school heads in making informed decisions about school culture and policy. By recognizing the significance of collaborative school culture and the need for stronger policy and training support, school

heads can advocate for systemic changes that prioritize socio-emotional learning. This may include allocating time for teacher collaboration, implementing school-wide SEL programs, and ensuring consistent access to training and resources that reinforce teachers' capacity to support students' emotional needs.

Future researchers

This study offers a foundational framework for future researchers interested in exploring students' socio-emotional development through the lens of teacher experiences. Future research could adopt a quantitative approach to determine the prevalence and effectiveness of the coping mechanisms identified in this study. Ad-

ditionally, longitudinal studies could examine socio-emotional strategies' impact on student outcomes and teacher well-being over time. Further research might explore how these approaches vary across cultural or socioeconomic contexts. In conclusion, these findings present an opportunity for a collaborative effort among educational leaders, school heads, teachers, and researchers to continue strengthening the support systems for socio-emotional development in elementary education. By applying these insights, educational systems can foster emotionally supportive environments that empower teachers and students to thrive.

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